

Taking a stand against the politicization of medical research: How “swinging the pendulum” poses a hazard to clinical trials, study participants, and the progress of science.

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Early in the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic, the drug hydroxychloroquine, which had been used for decades to treat malaria and autoimmune disorders, became a household name. Sattui and colleagues [1] describe the extremes of public discourse about hydroxychloroquine, from early enthusiasm to widespread skepticism. Throughout this “pendulum swing” of opinion, researchers worked to accrue increasingly definitive evidence about the safety and efficacy of hydroxychloroquine for different potential indications, such as pre-exposure prophylaxis (PrEP), post-exposure prophylaxis (PEP), early and mild disease treatment, and moderate or severe disease treatment. The “pendulum swing” of public discourse had profound effects on the ability to conduct clinical trials and ensure well-being of participants.

We experienced these challenges firsthand in our recently completed hydroxychloroquine PEP study, which enrolled participants across the United States [2]. It is important to add to Sattui et al’s review the impact of the “pendulum swing” on the progress of research and well-being of trial participants because of the profound implications for vaccine and treatment trials.

In February 2020, scientists in Wuhan, China reported that SARS-CoV-2 replication in Vero cells was inhibited by chloroquine [3]. Similar findings were published in mid-March with hydroxychloroquine [4]. In humans, early small studies raised the possibility that these drugs might reduce viral shedding and improve outcomes [5]. Facing an emergency, but armed only with this scant evidence, medical communities turned to hydroxychloroquine because of its wide availability and decades-long history of safe use to treat other conditions.

Fueled by the urgent need for definitive evidence, trials like ours launched rapidly, initially with high rates of enrollment. When public figures like US President Donald Trump and Tesla CEO Elon Musk began promoting the drug in March 2020, hydroxychloroquine prescriptions spiked so sharply that several States banned off-label prescribing to prevent drug shortages. For some study participants, clinical trials provided a way to access a suddenly scarce drug while also contributing to science.

In April, just as randomized trials were getting underway, two findings stoked unwarranted fear. A study from Brazil reported several cardiac deaths in older study participants receiving high-dose chloroquine [6]. The deaths were widely covered in the media, but lost in the messaging was the fact that most studies used the safer hydroxychloroquine at a much lower dose with a six-decade-long safety record. Soon afterward, an observational study from the Veterans Administration reported that severely ill patients given hydroxychloroquine had higher mortality rates [7], but the study was not randomized, leaving open the possibility that treated patients were sicker than untreated patients. Indeed, a July 2020 observational study [8] found the opposite trend – lower mortality among those receiving hydroxychloroquine. The scientific community recognized these limitations and remained supportive of research. However, the inconclusive evidence was portrayed in the media as proof that the public figures supporting the use of hydroxychloroquine were wrong. Our study experienced a sharp drop in recruitment, with some participants berating us for using “Trump’s drug.”

Then, on May 18th came the Surgisphere study: a large retrospective analysis published in *The Lancet* [9] which reported higher mortality rates in hydroxychloroquine-treated COVID-19 patients worldwide. While some scientists immediately identified suspicious inconsistencies in the publication,

writing an open letter to *The Lancet* to express their concerns, other scientists joined the growing movement to limit hydroxychloroquine research out of concern for safety.

Politics, too, played a role in the turning tide against hydroxychloroquine research. Just days before the Surgisphere publication, President Trump revealed, “I happen to be taking [hydroxychloroquine].” In our study recruitment, potential participants seemed to be increasingly polarized: insisting on either the drug’s benefit or its harm. Few remained in the middle, willing to volunteer for a fifty-fifty chance to receive drug or placebo.

Alarmingly, our study participants experienced social harms that were directly related to the politicization of hydroxychloroquine. One volunteer was shamed online, his portrait defaced with orange hair in likeness of President Trump. Another endured a verbal onslaught from peers claiming the study was a hoax aiming to sway the 2020 election. Investigators, too, were targeted with bots, negative comments, and harassment on social media.

Even as the pendulum began to return toward the middle, the damage to the progress of research could not be undone. Following the Surgisphere publication, hydroxychloroquine studies around the world paused enrollment to review safety data, and although the data ultimately supported continuing these studies, investigators struggled to recover the pace of recruitment. The Surgisphere study was subsequently retracted, but it was impossible to retract the suspicion it created, nor to recover the time lost. Multiple trials soon closed due to insufficient enrollment.

When the FDA revoked its EUA to use hydroxychloroquine for COVID-19 treatment or prevention except in the context of clinical trials, the last part of that message – that the FDA supported clinical trials – was lost in the media coverage. The drug had become so polarizing that even the FDA’s stated support for research was perceived in ways that hindered research.

The lessons from hydroxychloroquine’s “pendulum swing” go far beyond the need to await confirmed and peer-reviewed science. A major lesson is the danger of politicizing medical research, lest we hinder the very scientific progress that we need most. Already, politicization is emerging for other COVID-19 prevention and therapeutic candidates. In late July, President Trump spoke of an early COVID-19 vaccine candidate with the words, “we have a winner.” In August, media coverage of the FDA’s EUA for convalescent plasma focused mainly on the political pressure the agency faced in its decision. Similar concerns now abound regarding vaccine licensure.

Evidence-based medicine is our best tool to fight the COVID-19 pandemic. To ensure we have the study volunteers we will need – and to protect those volunteers – scientists must take a stand against politicization of research. Instead, given the current spotlight on clinical research, leaders and the media have an unparalleled opportunity to hold scientists accountable without undermining the scientific process, and to educate the public about the life-or-death importance of rigorous science. If “hydroxychloroquine” can become a household word in these unprecedented times, so too can the word “equipoise.”

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